

RESKILLING

Deliverable D2.3 Stakeholder Engagement Report

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List of Acronyms	
Acronym	Description
CCAM	Connected, Cooperative and Automated Mobility
CDE	Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation
DX.X	Deliverable X.X
ETT	Engagement Tracking Tool
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
SC	Stakeholder Community
WP	Work Package

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Executive Summary

Deliverable 2.3: Stakeholder Engagement Report summarises the RESKILLING stakeholder engagement results and outcomes to be exploited during and beyond the project lifetime. It is strongly connected to Deliverable 2.1: Stakeholder Mapping and Engagement Plan, which describes the processes established to build and maintain the RESKILLING Stakeholder Community (SC). This report presents the monitoring tools developed within the framework of the stakeholder engagement plan, and provides a performance overview, based on the data collected through these tools.

The report also outlines the conceptual and methodological background that guided the development of the monitoring tools and mechanisms, highlighting the challenge of tracking dynamic activities and human-centred processes and connections. The report proposes a structured approach to implement that monitoring process, addressing such complexities.

Finally, the report indicates the critical role of continuous stakeholder engagement assessment for the success of the RESKILLING research and innovation activities, also contributing to the long-term sustainability and impact of the project results.

This deliverable will be updated annually, starting in Month 12 (December 2025) as a milestone of the project, and a final version will be submitted as Deliverable 2.4: Update of Stakeholder Engagement Report at the end of the project.

1. Introduction

The “Research initiative for Enhancing and Adapting Workforce SKILLS for Implementing TraNsport Automation with Employment Growth (RESKILLING)” project is a European Commission-funded initiative under Horizon Europe. It brings together 20 partners with the aim of responding to a key challenge currently faced by Europe's mobility sector: to ensure that workers and businesses are equipped to thrive in the context of disruptive technological change, especially with the deployment of Connected, Cooperative and Automated Mobility (CCAM) solutions. In the context of the ongoing transformation of the mobility of people and goods due to automation and digitalisation, RESKILLING proposes a strategic, socially innovative approach to empower the sector's workforce, facilitate business model adaptation, and promote inclusive transitions that leave no one behind.

RESKILLING proposes the establishment of a comprehensive, multi-level framework to support territories and stakeholders in adapting to the socio-economic transformations associated with CCAM. The objective of the project is to propose, develop and validate a set of novel tools and services that enable workers, employers, authorities and intermediaries to navigate through and shape this shift. This includes analysing the impacts of CCAM across the entire value chain, designing pathways for skills development and redeployment, and fostering local innovation ecosystems that can actively drive and co-create the future of mobility.

RESKILLING is built around a Co-Innovation Framework that centres inclusiveness, co-creation, and social innovation across all phases of the project to ensure that all results are contextually grounded, human-centred, and collaboratively shaped. Stakeholder engagement in RESKILLING is a foundational pillar determining the project's goals and processes. To that end, Work Package 2 is specifically dedicated to mapping, engaging, and mobilising a wide spectrum of stakeholders – from transport workers and industry representatives, to social partners, training providers, researchers, and public authorities - with the goal of creating and nurturing a dedicated Stakeholder Community. Stakeholders are expected to play a key role in shaping the project's outputs through co-creation activities, sharing expertise, validating tools, and ensuring that results are relevant and replicable across Europe.

This deliverable (D2.3) shall ensure the success of stakeholder engagement within RESKILLING. This success will be measured through Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) reflecting the quality and quantity of engagement of external stakeholders (other than consortium members). It builds on the methodology defined in Deliverable 2.1: Stakeholder Mapping and Engagement Plan, supporting data collection on the implementation of tools and processes described. Beyond monitoring, it also identifies key exploitable results coming from stakeholder engagement, which will support post-project sustainability of the stakeholder community created in the RESKILLING project. By ensuring effective engagement activities within the project's Co-Innovation Framework, this report and its subsequent updates seek to operationalise the project's ambition: to make the CCAM transition socially inclusive, territorially responsive, and anchored in real-world needs and expertise.

1.1. Purpose of the Document

This deliverable is the first version of the Stakeholder engagement report and provides an overview of the current status of stakeholder engagement in the RESKILLING project, based on defined guidelines and measurement tools and procedures defined in D2.1: Stakeholder Engagement Plan. These tools and procedures rely on engagement metrics drawn from previous EU-funded research and have been adapted to the specific objectives and context of the RESKILLING project. In this deliverable, these metrics are presented and explained, and the tools set up to measure them are introduced. Since this is the first occurrence of this deliverable, most tools have only recently been deployed and thus do not yet provide substantial results. Subsequently, what is presented here corresponds to an early stage in the process of external stakeholder involvement. Future versions of the deliverable will provide a more detailed and quantitative assessment of engagement status and performance.

Engagement efforts have already begun however, based on an initial outreach, focusing on awareness raising regarding the scope and ambitions of RESKILLING. The main objective in this first phase is to establish contact and lay the foundation for structured and solid collaboration that will gradually evolve into a robust and interconnected stakeholder community. This community and its sustainability represent one of the key intended impacts of the RESKILLING project, extending beyond the project lifetime.

This report also outlines early progress in the development of the RESKILLING Stakeholder Community and how this network can contribute and support broader European policy goals in the longer term and in relation to skills development, sustainable transitions, and inclusive innovation.

To summarise, this Stakeholder Engagement Report provides a first assessment of external stakeholder engagement within the project, introduces the monitoring framework and tools, and describes the intended contribution to building a lasting and impactful stakeholder ecosystem.

1.2. Intended Audience

This deliverable is intended for three main audiences: the RESKILLING Partners, the European Commission and key stakeholders involved in the deployment of CCAM, and last for research organisations looking for stakeholder engagement monitoring methodologies.

The RESKILLING partners will find in this deliverable an overview of the results of their work when it comes to stakeholder engagement. The first occurrence of the deliverable will help them understand how their actions will be measured and what are the objectives of the processes and tools set up in WP2. Subsequent versions will provide them with insights into the effectiveness of their relevant actions, helping them identify areas for improvement and further engagement. The final version will serve as a consolidated report and reference for future initiatives beyond the project's duration.

For the European Commission, this deliverable offers an idea of the stakeholder engagement outcomes generated by the RESKILLING project and defines outcomes to be exploited later on within EU-funded research, as well as in any activity supporting CCAM deployment and requiring stakeholder involvement. The main actors of CCAM deployment in Europe and beyond, such as authorities, services, vehicle and infrastructure manufacturers and managers, and user representatives - among others -, will also find an interest in this deliverable, to guide their own

stakeholder engagement strategies, support inclusive consultation processes, and build on existing connections, in order to ensure a just transition to automated mobility services.

Finally, for research-carrying organisations, this deliverable offers a replicable methodology for monitoring stakeholder engagement, presenting KPIs and data collection processes, as well as reporting mechanisms developed within the RESKILLING project. It also showcases preliminary results and describes challenges faced.

1.3. Interrelations

The RESKILLING Stakeholder Engagement Report draws from activities conducted in all project's WPs. At its foundation, the report is based on the stakeholder mapping developed in Task 2.1 of **WP2: Stakeholder Community Engagement**, which defines and organises stakeholder categories to engage in the project activities. It is also closely aligned with the Stakeholder Engagement Plan presented in D2.1, prepared in the framework of Task 2.2, which defines the methodology and strategic approach for stakeholder engagement. Moreover, the report draws on activities of Tasks 2.4 and 2.5, which focus on the engagement of the Advisory Board and the development of strategic collaborations, both of which being essential components in establishing a concrete and influential stakeholder ecosystem around the project.

The current iteration of D2.3 includes data on the first stakeholder engagement activities carried out in the project, during its awareness raising phase. These activities are coordinated under **WP6: Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation**. Continuous collaboration with this WP is therefore essential to ensure that monitoring tools remain updated and aligned with dissemination and exploitation efforts, and to reinforce the stakeholder engagement key exploitable results.

Further on in the project, collaboration with multiple WPs will be necessary to ensure up to date versions of the report:

- **WP3 – Short-, medium- and long-term employment and socio-economic effects of CCAM.** Stakeholders provide input through a variety of methods, including interviews, surveys and participatory scenario-building exercises.
- **WP4 – Towards job creation, growth and innovation.** The focus is on co-designing business model development and innovation toolkits, a mission-oriented approach to social, technological and training innovation, as well as training pathways.
- **WP5 – Impact Assessment & Roadmap.** This is the stage at which stakeholders are involved in defining recommendations to best evaluate the socio-economic impacts of CCAM deployment on employment, education and training.

2. Theoretical background to measure engagement

Measuring engagement means to define a structured scale that captures different levels of engagement, and indicators showing that a given level has been reached. This will allow for a harmonised and consistent assessment of progress, helping also to identify where additional efforts are needed.

However, this scale may vary depending on two main criteria: (1) the stage of engagement within the project duration, and (2) the measurement perspective adopted. These two criteria are explained below, with the different levels they can represent in a scale. After that, a list of KPIs is proposed to anticipate how stakeholder engagement will be assessed throughout the RESKILLING project. These KPIs will facilitate both qualitative and quantitative dimensions of engagement and will serve as the basis for constant monitoring and evaluation.

2.1. Stages of engagement

In the Stakeholder Engagement Plan (D2.1), the cyclical process of stakeholder engagement for policy design and strategic foresight was described based on stages in the planning of stakeholder engagement: first stakeholder mapping, then co-working with them on project outcomes, and finally validating results with them.

Another perspective however is the stages of engagement with the project for the stakeholders themselves. For an external stakeholder, engagement with the RESKILLING project will also follow a progressive approach based on different stages.

Stage 1 – Awareness

In that first stage, stakeholders discover the project. They are reached out to by the partners and their attention is solicited for the first time. They need to get to know the project before their interest is sparked.

1. In that stage, the first level of engagement is a passive outreach, where stakeholders have been identified (or reached in a wider campaign) and have received information on the project or a specific activity. The passive outreach level is the initial step in raising awareness – the stakeholder is aware that the project exists, and the project has identified and included the stakeholder in its relevant contacts.
2. The second level of engagement in the awareness stage is an expression of interest from the stakeholder side. The stakeholder takes a step to show their interest in the project, by answering an invitation, registering to an event or activity, reacting to an outreach from the project.

Stage 2 – Co-creation

In that second stage, stakeholders transition from awareness to active membership in the RESKILLING Stakeholders Community because they have expressed interest and have already engaged with the project, through reaction, answer, or participation in project event(s). At this point, they are considered engaged participants and need to be further integrated into the project's co-creation processes to contribute meaningfully to its outcomes. The objective of this stage is to encourage their involvement into project activities, such as co-thinking, co-designing, co-creating, validating outputs, sharing feedback, and contributing to the continuous improvement of project results.

1. In that stage, the first level of engagement is participation and contribution as framed by the project. It means that stakeholders have joined organised activities by the project and completed actions as requested – for example filling survey(s), answering an interview, joining a focus group.
2. The second level of engagement corresponds to active inputs provision, where stakeholders show inspiration from the project works and bring additional insights enriching the project work, beyond foreseen participation.

Stage 3 – Empowerment

In the last engagement stage from a stakeholder perspective, stakeholders take ownership of engagement and initiate actions leading to a wider outreach and impact of the project. This is the empowerment stage.

1. In that stage, the first level is the suggestion of additional activities and opportunities to the project partners, based on the stakeholder participation and observation of RESKILLING work and results.
2. The second engagement level of the empowerment stage is a decisive support in dissemination through the stakeholder’s channels and networks.
3. The last engagement level is an active connection setup with relevant contacts to support the RESKILLING work development and expansion.

Most of the stakeholders involved in strategic collaboration of the RESKILLING project (Advisory Board, CCAM Partnership,...) are expected to reach the last stage of engagement with the RESKILLING project.

Table 1 Stakeholder Engagement Stages. Source: POLIS, 2025

Stages	1. Awareness	2. Co-creation	3. Empowerment
Level of Engagement	1 – Passive outreach	1 – Participation & contribution	1 – Additional suggestions
	2 – Expression of interest	2 – Active inputs provision	2 – Dissemination support
			3 – Active connection setup

2.2. Measuring perspective

Beyond the different stages of engagement which determine specific engagement level options, it became evident in the stage definition that perspective (project or stakeholders one) was key to assess engagement. Indeed, stages to engage stakeholders from the project perspective differ from the stages of being engaged from the stakeholders perspective. Therefore, the indicators and metrics established to measure engagement should be representative of various perspectives in order to ensure stakeholder engagement success.

For the project, a wide engagement and in-depth relevant contributions are key to show stakeholder engagement success.

For stakeholders, benefits they draw from their participation are important, as well as how their participation is valued, and how easy participation processes are. These are other indicators, which are nonetheless as important as the project perspective ones.

To ensure a representative assessment of stakeholder engagement, RESKILLING defines both quantitative and qualitative indicators based on three perspectives: a single activity or channel

perspective, the global project perspective, and the stakeholders' perspective. Below are some examples to clarify the distinctions and relevance of each perspective.

Quantitative stakeholder engagement assessment

- **From an activity or channel perspective**

This metric would cover the number of stakeholders joining, registered, viewing, or reacting, the number of countries covered among these stakeholders, and the number of stakeholder categories they represent, among others.

- **From a project perspective**

Quantitative measurement would relate to the number of engagement activities organised, the number of engagement tools set up, and for each tool the number of actions undertaken (posting news, uploading content, sending an email...).

- **From a stakeholder perspective**

Quantitative assessment of engagement would refer to the number of interactions with the project, the level of engagement (from passive attendance to inputs provision and external dissemination), and the satisfaction level of having engaged with the project.

Qualitative stakeholder engagement assessment

- **From an activity or channel perspective**

Qualitative metrics would be based on the relevance of engagement, which corresponds to what it brings to the activity or channel outcome (e.g., innovative idea on a research question, activity spark on a LinkedIn post, etc.).

- **From a project perspective**

Quality of engagement can be connected with the recurrence of participation and support to the stakeholder community reinforcement.

- **From a stakeholder perspective**

Quality of engagement refers to the benefits effectively retrieved from participating.

2.3. Key Performance Indicators

The KPIs defined in this part concretely describe how RESKILLING will measure stakeholder engagement performance from the different perspectives presented above and considering the different stages introduced. These KPIs also draw on stakeholder engagement strategies used in previous research and innovation works.

To measure these KPIs, specific tools have been set up: The Repository and the Engagement Tracking Tool (ETT). The KPIs are valid across engagement stages, but different tools are used to measure them at different stages. In addition, different tools collect data for these KPIs considering different perspectives. These tools are presented in section 3 Stakeholder Engagement Assessment Tools.

A final report will be prepared to ensure that the outcomes of the stakeholder community building work conducted in RESKILLING are further exploited beyond the project lifetime. This is detailed in section 4 Stakeholder Engagement Legacy.

Table 2 Stakeholder Engagement Indicators. Source: POLIS, 2025

KPI	Definition	Perspective	Quantitative/Qualitative & Collecting Tool
Stakeholder Engagement Volume	Total number of participants, views on a post, or clicks on a webpage	Activity/Channel	Quantitative → ETT
	Number of stakeholder engagement initiatives undertaken	Project	Quantitative → ETT
Stakeholder Engagement Diversity	Number of participants / engaged stakeholders by category	Activity/Channel & Project	Quantitative → ETT
	Number of engaged stakeholders by country	Activity/Channel & Project	Quantitative → ETT
Stakeholder Engagement Reliability	Number of interactions within an activity / channel or with the project overall	Stakeholder	Quantitative & Qualitative → ETT & Repository
	Percentage of involved stakeholders who are returning	Activity/Channel	Quantitative & Qualitative → ETT & Repository
Stakeholder Engagement Relevance	Engagement stage of each stakeholder	Project	Qualitative → Repository
	Level of participation of each stakeholder	Activity/Channel	Qualitative → Repository
	RESKILLING Partners satisfaction by stakeholder contributions	Activity/Channel	Qualitative → Repository
Stakeholder Engagement Satisfaction	Satisfaction level of engaged stakeholders	Stakeholder, Activity/Channel & Project	Quantitative & Qualitative → ETT & Repository
Stakeholder Engagement Legacy	Number of stakeholder engagement tools setup	Project	Quantitative → Final Report
	Post-project hosting solutions for RESKILLING Stakeholder Community tools	Project	Qualitative → Final Report

3. Stakeholder Engagement Assessment Tools

3.1. Tools measuring awareness stage engagement

As part of the first level of stakeholder engagement, individuals and organisations will be exposed to the project, learn about its objectives, and consider their potential interest in engaging further. To support this phase, several communication and dissemination tools have been developed and monitored, in cooperation with WP6, to assess the scope, diversity, and initial responsiveness of the target stakeholder community. These tools are essential to build visibility, trigger curiosity, and initiate first contact with relevant actors across sectors and geographic areas. They are described in D6.1: Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation (CDE) strategy.

Each of these channels contributes to raising awareness and is assessed using specific metrics outlined in the KPIs (Section 2.3). Below, we outline the main awareness tools used in this initial engagement stage:

Communication & Dissemination channels performance

- Website

The RESKILLING project website (available at <https://reskilling-project.eu/>) serves as the main information hub and public-facing digital entry point for all stakeholders. It offers a comprehensive overview of the project's mission, partners, and activities, with dedicated sections for news, deliverables, events, and stakeholder engagement.

A stakeholder-specific section has been integrated into the site to outline:

- The benefits of joining the Stakeholder Community,
- Ongoing and upcoming engagement opportunities,
- A user-friendly registration form allowing stakeholders to signal their interest and thematic preferences.

- Newsletter

The RESKILLING newsletter is a key communication tool to keep stakeholders informed about project progress, upcoming engagement activities, and relevant developments in the CCAM and labour transition landscape. It is distributed twice per year to a growing audience comprising stakeholder belonging to groups defined during the mapping. The newsletter has been integrated into the project's dedicated LinkedIn account using a native platform feature. This approach leverages the strong performance of the LinkedIn page to maximise visibility and engage a broad range of stakeholders. To ensure accessibility for those not active on LinkedIn, each newsletter edition is also made available on the project website under the dedicated "[Newsletters](#)" section. Additionally, subscribers to the website (i.e., those who have registered via the [website Subscription form](#)) will be notified of each new release via email, either through a PDF attachment, a direct link to the Newsletters section, or in HTML format.

The newsletter functions as both a push channel (for updates) and a trigger for action (event registration, content interaction, forum engagement). KPIs include the number of subscribers, and open and click-through rates.

- **Social media**

RESKILLING maintains a LinkedIn page as its primary social media channel. It is used to increase visibility, share updates, and drive traffic to other engagement opportunities (e.g. registration form, events, publications, compilation of survey useful for project activities). In Year 1, the focus is on building an initial professional followers basis, engaging with relevant communities, and prompting reactions that mark early interest.

LinkedIn is also used to amplify the reach of newsletters and invitations to co-creation activities. In addition, dedicated accounts on X (formerly Twitter), Facebook, and YouTube have been established to engage a broader audience and diversify outreach efforts. A Zenodo Community is also planned to be set up to facilitate open access to project outputs. Furthermore, RESKILLING uses the communication channels of its consortium partners to further leverage and disseminate key messages and reach their respective stakeholder communities.

- **Physical events and conferences**

In-person events are central to the RESKILLING awareness and engagement strategy. Attendance at key sectoral conferences and transport-focused events will ensure visibility among critical actors who may not yet be engaged digitally. These tasks will be carried out together with the coordinator of the project, as well as leading partners of the different WP, especially WP6 focusing on communication and dissemination.

Dissemination materials (e.g. flyers, roll-ups), one-on-one networking, and conference presentations serve as awareness tools, in addition to deeper engagement tools at later stages of the project.

Stakeholder Forum performance

A dedicated online Stakeholder Forum is being designed to provide a private, collaborative space for registered members of the RESKILLING Stakeholder Community. While the platform is technically available, no external stakeholder content has yet been posted, as the forum is currently in its onboarding phase. This Forum is designed to foster informal dialogue, structured input collection, and ongoing engagement, and will act as both a communication channel and a collaborative workspace with stakeholders.

The platform will include:

- Thematic discussion spaces aligned with stakeholder interests (e.g. labour and skills, training innovation, business models, policy and governance), where WP leads can share targeted content or questions.
- Announcements and event invitations, including open calls for co-creation workshops, survey participation, use case feedback, or piloting opportunities.
- Personalised engagement feeds, where stakeholders see updates and opportunities relevant to their profile.
- Resource sharing functionalities (documents, toolkits, deliverables), enabling stakeholders to access and comment on project outputs.
- Embedded polls, forms, and reactions, allowing continuous light-feedback mechanisms without the need for formal data collection events.

This tool is expected to support all three engagement stages, not only awareness but also co-creation, and empowerment, providing continuity and context for stakeholder interactions over time. Initial

onboarding will be supported by email invitations and tailored explanations of the platform's purpose, benefits, and structure.

To implement the Stakeholder Forum, the project will deploy based on the platform [BetterMode](#), a secure, modular online community platform that offers significantly more functionality and flexibility than traditional social media groups.

BetterMode was selected for its ability to host customisable, role-based access across thematic discussion spaces, enabling WP leads and project partners to interact with different stakeholder sub-groups in tailored ways. Unlike LinkedIn, which is oriented toward broadcast communication and informal networking, BetterMode supports structured content delivery, in-platform document hosting, polling tools, and customisable workflows, which are essential for the co-creation and validation processes required throughout RESKILLING. Its dashboard and analytics features will also allow the Consortium to monitor engagement patterns over time, supporting the measurement of key engagement indicators. Importantly, the platform allows for the embedding of lightweight interaction tools—such as surveys, feedback forms, and reaction buttons—which lowers barriers to participation while collecting usable input. Its private community environment ensures a focused space for collaboration beyond what public social networks can offer, and allows for sustained relationship-building and knowledge exchange across all engagement stages.

CCAM Partnership Engagement

CCAM Partnership represents a strategic dissemination and awareness platform, especially given that RESKILLING partners are embedded in its Cluster 6 on societal aspects and user needs. Awareness actions in this channel include:

- Presentations of RESKILLING objectives and activities in CCAM cluster meetings;
- Circulation of project materials through internal CCAM communication channels;
- Direct invitations to CCAM Partnership members to join the Stakeholder Community;
- Use of shared LinkedIn audiences and mailing networks.

3.2. Tools monitoring co-creation stage engagement

Once stakeholders move beyond awareness and express interest in engaging with the RESKILLING project, the focus shifts to monitoring how they contribute to shaping project outcomes. This co-creation stage relies on structured participation through targeted activities (e.g., interviews, surveys, workshops), and is assessed via three complementary tools.

The Stakeholder Table

This tool is used to track engagement per stakeholder sub-category, to ensure coverage across all identified target groups and maintain consistency with the stakeholder ontology developed in D2.1.

Quantitative and Qualitative metrics

- Number of stakeholder categories engaged (per year)
- Number of sub-groups reached
- Number of stakeholders per sub-category
- Geographic coverage (per country, per region)
- Gender balance

- Number of project activities involving each sub-category
- Fit of stakeholder engagement with task objectives (relevance matrix)
- Level of engagement diversity across deliverables

The Stakeholder Repository

The Repository tracks all stakeholder entries at the individual/organisational level, capturing background data, engagement potential, and interactions over time. It provides insight into who is being reached, how they were approached, and their level of involvement. This tool is an Excel table collecting data, which will follow all GDPR processes and rules, as well as the Data Management Process described in D1.3.

Quantitative and qualitative metrics:

- Number of entries by stakeholder type and country
- Distribution of interests (skills, training, business models, etc.)
- Number of stakeholders per communication channel (email, LinkedIn, event)
- Response rates (Confirmed / Declined / No reply)
- Number of stakeholders marked “Engaged in activity = Yes”
- Levels of engagement
- Relevant quotes or expressions of interest
- Stakeholder type mapping against engagement depth

The Engagement Tracking Tool

This tool allows WP leads and task managers to log each co-creation activity, monitor who participated, and assess the diversity and quality of the engagement.

Quantitative and qualitative metrics:

- Total number of participants per activity
- Returning participant ratio
- Participation rate by stakeholder type (e.g. # of unions vs. employers)
- Gender balance among participants (to be completed as feasible)
- Number of activities by format (online / physical)
- Participation by Task and WP over time
- Type of engagement per event (e.g., dialogue, knowledge-sharing, co-design)
- Stakeholder satisfaction (via feedback forms or verbal debriefs)
- Relevance of contributions made during events
- Ability of activities to reach underrepresented groups

- Specific engagement outcomes (e.g., insight adopted into WP3 modelling, input leading to WP4 training adaptation)

4. Stakeholder Engagement Legacy

RESKILLING's stakeholder engagement strategy is not limited to participation during the project's lifetime. Rather, it is designed to generate a lasting legacy through the development of a sustainable, structured, and interconnected ecosystem of stakeholders capable of supporting the transition to inclusive and innovation-driven workforce adaptation in the CCAM domain. This section outlines how key components of the engagement architecture, namely the Stakeholder Community (SC), oriented toward long-term sustainability and integration in European mobility and skills policy frameworks.

4.1. RESKILLING Stakeholder Community

To ensure the sustainability of the Stakeholder Community beyond the project, several legacy-oriented mechanisms have been established:

- **Stakeholder-driven governance structures:** By involving SC members in co-creation activities, workshops, the Advisory Board, and targeted consultations, RESKILLING empowers them to shape project outputs. This shared ownership fosters continuity and encourages further collaboration beyond the project.
- **Integration with permanent platforms:** Selected outputs—such as the CCAM Employment & Skills Observatory—are being designed for integration into ongoing networks or initiatives and thus supporting continued use and updates after project's completion in 2027.
- **Open formats and replicability:** RESKILLING's engagement tools defined in D2.1 are open-access and transferable. These can be adopted or adapted by other CCAM-related projects and institutions.
- **Training and upskilling pathways:** Stakeholders engaged in RESKILLING will have access to co-developed training materials and methodologies, increasing their long-term capacity to participate in similar projects or transition initiatives.
- **Community self-activation channels:** Through the Stakeholder Forum (BetterMode platform), members will be able to exchange independently, announce their own events, and propose new initiatives linked to workforce adaptation and CCAM.

The legacy will be supported by the updated versions of this deliverable and the Stakeholder Community engagement plans, to be outlined in collaboration with project partners from WP5 and WP6.

4.2. RESKILLING Strategic connections

Advisory Board

The Advisory Board plays a critical role in amplifying the project's strategic foresight and ensuring alignment with current developments and fostering external relevance. To ensure its legacy:

- The AB has been equipped with operational guidelines and a timeline for engagement across the project.
- Members are drawn from global experts in CCAM, labour, industry, and SSH fields, many of whom are part of permanent institutions or EU-level bodies.
- Selected AB members will be invited to continue advising or integrating RESKILLING results into national or European strategies after the project ends.
- Reviews by the AB feed into policy recommendations and may support their formal uptake into public or sectoral roadmaps.

International Cooperation

International cooperation is designed to provide the project with mutual learning, alignment with global frameworks, and strategic positioning of results in broader employment and innovation discussions around global automated mobility. These include annual virtual concertation meetings, engagement with global conferences and bodies, as well as using partners international memberships to maintain and institutionalise relationships with third-country R&D centres, national authorities, and mobility networks.

The legacy dimension of this international strand is reinforced through:

- Systematic documentation, reporting co-creation and communication of insights through the Forum.
- Promotion of common language and comparable methodologies for skills assessment and employment transitions.
- Opportunities for mutual contribution to training schemes, policy roadmaps, and even observatory functionalities, ensuring that RESKILLING outputs remain relevant.

Related projects and initiatives

To maximise alignment and legacy:

- RESKILLING has initiated dialogue with projects under the CCAM Partnership (e.g., CCAM-ERAS) and other Horizon Europe and/or CCAM partnership funded initiatives (e.g., being listed as an [Associated Project](#) under the [DS4Skills](#) initiative). These dialogues will inform relevant upcoming projects as well.
- Bilateral cooperation mechanisms (shared workshops, peer-reviews, mutual invitations) are being developed to facilitate cross-project uptake of outputs.
- The Stakeholder Community will be extended to stakeholders from these projects, creating synergies and widening long-term usability of RESKILLING's results.

CCAM Partnership collaboration

A key pillar of strategic sustainability is the close connection with the CCAM Partnership:

- Through partners like VTI (co-lead of Cluster 6) and others partners, the project will ensure ongoing feedback loops between our results and CCAM priorities.
- RESKILLING findings on workforce profiles, training ecosystems, and KPI frameworks will be made available to the Partnership for standardisation and integration into future R&I agendas.

- The project's stakeholder tools and methodologies can serve as blueprints for other CCAM-funded initiatives.
- Regular participation in CCAM events and working groups will allow continuous visibility, dialogue, and updates on project outputs post-2027.

5. Next Steps

The RESKILLING Stakeholder Engagement Report represents quite a challenging activity: to translate human activity into numbers and measurable variables, in order to monitor the success of engagement of relevant actors in the project work. Awareness, Information, Consultation, Involvement and Co-creation are theoretical concepts which require practical implementation, and this transition is difficult to measure. Therefore, assessment tools which have been meticulously designed, will be updated in the course of the project, and are carefully implemented as explained below.

5.1. Implementation and Updates

Tools' update procedure

All tools mentioned in sections 3 and 4 are set up in the first six months of the project. Awareness raising engagement started from the first month, while co-creation concretely begins during the investigation work of the project a few months later. Since both will go on across the whole project duration, all engagement assessment tools will require adaptation.

Monitoring data on the awareness stage (including information about engagement on the website and social media) will be maintained within the WP6 tools. ECTRI and CERTH will monitor engagement on the RESKILLING website thanks to the website backend data. ECTRI and POLIS will follow social media engagement based on data saved on the platforms. Engagement results will be included in semi-annual technical reports and updates of the CDE strategy at months 18 and 27, and reported annually at milestones 28, 29 and 30: Wide outreach of project scope and results.

The tools monitoring co-creation with the stakeholders will be tested during the first activities and adapted if needed, in order to ensure that monitoring can be consistent across the whole project duration.

Finally, the stakeholder engagement legacy tools will also evolve with project activities: members in the Advisory Board could be replaced in case of position change, international cooperation could have shifting focuses depending on international relations status, the CCAM Partnership collaboration will of course take different forms based on activities and future development of the CCAM Partnership itself. Therefore, the monitoring process will also be adapted.

Monitoring results

Monitoring performance will be done by all partners, who will contribute to all the tools described in sections 3 and 4, in order to enrich maximum outreach of the project and accuracy of data. A monthly WP2 call will ensure that these tools are up-to-date. In parallel, WP6 takes care of the monitoring of the awareness stage tools such as the website, social media, and dissemination events.

The overall result from each tool will be submitted to the European Commission at the end of the project in Deliverable 2.4: Update of Stakeholder Engagement Report. It will also be included in yearly

updates of this deliverable, which are not official deliverables, but key milestones of the project. These subsequent versions of D2.3 will be prepared once a year starting from Month 12 (December 2025).

Strengthening the tools

To ensure the monitoring tools are efficient, feedback will be sought from all partners contributing in the monthly WP2 calls and WP6 calls. As introduced here, the process of keeping track of human engagement is a challenging one, causing fundamental needs for collaboration, flexibility, and adaptation. Therefore, the tools will be used to monitor and require coherence in the course of the project, but also adaptation to the evolutions of the project stakeholder engagement situation.

5.2. Risk Management

With any challenging process come specific risks. Four main risks have been identified in the stakeholder engagement monitoring and reporting activity, which are exposed below.

Tools' usage related risks

The usage of the tools presents a risk, because all partners should use them, so instructions must be very clear, and there is a risk that understanding or interpretation varies from one partner to another. The monthly calls should ensure clarifications. This risk has a moderated chance of materialising.

In addition, there might be a risk of lacking completion by some partners. Reminders sent by emails will be a first mitigation measure, monthly calls will be a second one, and individual meetings might be a last resource before calling on the project coordinator for moderation. In parallel, the tools can be adapted with feedback from partners, to ensure the data collection process is as smooth as possible and facilitates all partners' contribution. This risk has a low chance of materialising.

Tools' structure related risks

Since the monitoring tools are new ones and created before the real engagement with stakeholder starts, there is a risk that the data collection process is not well adapted to monitor engagement. Though the tools are based on literature review and consultation with partners, they can always be updated with feedback from partners, by email, and during the monthly calls. This risk has a high chance of happening, but mitigation is rather easy.

To anticipate this risk and minimise its severity, the tools' structure should remain flexible. This means that changing their structure should be done considering the potential impacts on the relevance of previous results. For example, a decision to collect additional or less data should ensure that the data collected in the future would still be usable and comparable with data already collected. This will be considered at any structure adaptation.

Tools' support related risks

Another risk related to stakeholder engagement monitoring and reporting is the support to ensure efficiency of the reporting tools. Some of these tools are quite technical, such as the Stakeholder Forum platform, and require an expertise to retrieve relevant and updated information, best reflecting the real status of stakeholder engagement in the RESKILLING project. This expertise might sometimes require external support and incur budget needs. This risk has a moderate chance to materialise. A mitigation option is to ensure provisional budget for this type of challenge. Another one is to involve internal experts within partner organisations along the development and use of these

more technical tools, to ensure they can support when a challenge arises. POLIS, CERTH, and ECTRI have relevant departments and experts in this, already involved in the website and social media development for the RESKILLING project. Their involvement reduces the probability of this risk, and increases the protection capacity of the project as well.

Engagement status related risks

A last risk identified in the setup of stakeholder engagement monitoring and report processes is related to a lack of interest and investment of external stakeholders in the RESKILLING activities and community. This could weaken the stakeholder community and endanger its existence and maintenance beyond the project lifetime, reducing the short, medium and long term impacts of the RESKILLING outcomes. The probability of this risk is moderate. To minimise the severity of that risk, the strategic collaborations described in part 4.2 will be instrumental, as well as key connections in the partners' networks. In addition, exploiting momentums is a good leverage of engagement, such as political, legislative, or social situations, which cause transformations and challenge status quo for the CCAM, jobs, and skills stakeholders. Finally, RESKILLING will engage with related initiatives to ensure a common approach of stakeholders and avoid duplication. A first step in that direction is the collaboration established with the CCAM-ERAS project.

6. Conclusion

Deliverable 2.3: Stakeholder Engagement Report has a key role in the RESKILLING work. It is not solely a report, but also an instrument to monitor and ensure a successful basis for project activities enabling innovation and relevant results.

The report is a picture of underground work conducted by the WP2 leader but also all partners completing the tools and providing feedback to ensure the project reflects adequately stakeholder engagement. This work is mostly included in the monitoring tools, although these tools will not reflect content produced with stakeholder involvement.

The report is edited every year to ensure results are constantly assessed and any challenge is addressed in time.

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